

Culture of Human Behavior in Architecture

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ABSTRACT: The basic process that involves human interaction with their environment is environmental information obtained by the process of perception. Perception is formed because of the interaction of a person (individual) with their life space, which is finally realised in behavioral attitudes. Thus, the behavior, response, and action are determined by personal perception. It can be argued that human psychiatry determines human behavior in the form of condition, attitude, perception, cognition, and motivation. Cognition is obtained from the culture, experience, and education that an individual owns. The aspect of cognition is an aspect of change movement because the information received determines the feeling and the willingness to do. In terms of cognition, it consists of several components, namely cognitive components that will answer the question of what people think about objects. The components of affection conation will answer what is felt (happy / not happy) to the object, and it will answer the question of the willingness to act toward the object. Each component does not stand alone, but one unity is called the cognition system. The cognition system is the result of a cognitive process. It comprises perception activities, imagination, thinking, reasoning, and decision-making.

KEYWORDS: Architecture, Behavior, Environmental, Human, Perception.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic process of human interaction with the environment is environmental information obtained through perception. It is explained that a person's perception is determined by experience and that experience is influenced by culture and cultural influence, which includes living habits (Suwondo, 1986).

Perceptions are formed due to the interaction of a person (individual) with their life space which ultimately manifests in behavioral attitudes. Thus, the behavior behind human attitudes, responses, and actions is largely determined by the personal perception of the person concerned. It can be said that human behavior is determined by the psychological conditions within humans in the form of attitudes, perceptions, cognition, and motivation. Cognition is obtained from an individual's culture, experience, and education. The cognitive aspect is the driving aspect of change because the information received determines feelings and willingness to act. In terms of cognition, it consists of several components, namely the cognition component, which will answer the question of what one thinks or perceives about objects. The affective conation component will answer what one feels (happy/displeased) about the object, and the conation component will answer the question of how willingness to act on an object.

Each of these components does not stand alone but forms a unit called a cognitive system. The cognitive system is the result of a cognitive process consisting of the activities of perception, imagination, thinking, reasoning and decision-making.

Lang further stated that we could not understand a person's behavior regarding space and place without understanding the cognitive map image that they obtain and then use (John Lang, 1978).

In a pair of intertwined, all these factors as a system will influence how people will perceive an environment, as in the relationship in the scheme below. Perception is an important element in spatial psychology. Perception is the meaning of observation results through absorbing information about the surrounding environment through the five senses, including perceptions of the overall environment. The environment in which an individual is raised can briefly be interpreted as an observation/observation that is directly linked to meaning. Environmental conditions are stimuli for a perception process. After receiving stimulation, in the next stage, selection occurs, which interacts with interpretation. Interpretation depends on experience (recent experience). From this interaction process, a response is formed in the form of (permanent memory) which is called mental representation. Each human's perception will always be different or very subjective because perception depends on the human perceiver.

II. HUMAN AND ARCHITECTURE

Basically, human needs will always develop according to the demands of their personality. This is explained by Maslow's theory, the hierarchy of human needs according to the pyramid (from base to top), consisting of Physiological Needs, Security Needs, Socialization Needs, Esteem Needs, and Self-Actualization Needs (Clovis, 1977).

Humans as rational creatures are different from humans as rational creatures. Ratio here means it does not depend on the situation, while common sense depends on the situation. As rational creatures, humans tend always to try to understand their environment. And the tendency to always understand the environment is one of the characteristics of humans. However, the balance that humans seek is never the same for everyone because, in psychology, the proposition is also known that each person is a unique individual who has his or her own way of reacting to the environment. Environmental psychology is a science that studies the responses given by living creatures to their environment (Sarlito, 1992).

In Psychology: A Study of Mental Life, Woodworth and Marquis stated that psychology can be defined as the science of the individual's activities. The word activity is used here in a very broad sense. It includes not only motor activities like walking and speaking but also cognitive (knowledge-getting) activities like seeing, hearing, remembering, and thinking, and emotional activities like laughing and crying and feeling happy or sad.

Meanwhile, Bell stated that environmental psychology is the science of the interrelationship between behavior and the artificial and natural environment. Holahan stated that environmental psychology is a field of psychology that specifically examines the relationship between the physical environment and human behavior and experience (Holahan, 1982).

Because environmental psychology processing is not only about human behavior but also the relationship between human behavior and its physical environment. Kurt Lewin formulated that behavior is a function of the person's personal circumstances and the environment in which the person is.

Architectural design includes programming, planning, and design stages. Programming is concerned primarily with collecting and organizing information required in building design. One of the most crucial pieces of information at this programming stage is the client (building user). Who the people are, their background, demographic characteristics, behavioral patterns, philosophy, history of operations, client development, and so on. Good architects, from the major construction projects of the Gothic era to the humanists of our era, are very sensitive to the determinants of architecture. The best buildings of historical times responded to human needs and feelings, not only in their era but also as societal lifestyles developed.

However, many buildings fail functionally or behaviorally. Other buildings that are considered successful could actually be designed more successfully if the architect paid attention to users' needs and to the ways in which the built environment and behavior interact with each other.

In the cyclic diagram first proposed by architectural sociologist John Ziesel, information and concepts of environmental behavior have no place in the design process. Instead, they make policies and programming and are always thorough, and such decisions and designs are assessed against social behavior criteria in post-occupancy assessments. Human interaction with the environment (Snyder, 1979).

III. BEHAVIOR AND ENVIRONMENTAL PERCEPTION

The theory of the relationship between behavior and the environment consists of nature and function, theoretical approaches such as the environmental stress approach, arousal approach, environmental content approach, surface adaptation theory, and integration (Snyder, 1979).

Behavioral relationship theory consists of Function theory, Approach, and Integration. The human answer (response) to the environment around him depends on how the human perceives the environment. There are several human perceptions of the environment, namely:

A. Personal Space

Humans perceive the space around them as a whole. If the contents of the space are other people, then people will immediately create distance between themselves and those other people.

According to Holahan, there are four types of personal space (Holahan, 1982), namely:

1. Intimate distance (0-0.50m): namely, the distance for contact with friends or family members.
2. Personal distance (0.5-1.30m): namely, the distance for conversation between two close friends

familiar.

3. Social distance (1.30-4.00m): namely the distance for formal relationships, namely business and others other.
4. Public distance (4.00-8.30m): namely, the distance for more formal relationships such as lectures and others.

The differences in distance mentioned above are also determined by gender, age, personality, ethnicity or ethnic background, and the surrounding environmental conditions.

B. Privacy

It is a symptom of reducing external interference towards oneself to a minimum level or a desire or tendency for oneself not to be disturbed by one's solitude. There are two groups, namely:

1. The desire not to be physically disturbed. This group consists of three types: the desire to be alone (solitude), the desire to stay away from sight and distraction (seclusion), and the desire to be intimate (intimacy).
2. The desire to maintain one's own confidentiality is manifested in the behavior of only providing information that is deemed necessary.

C. Territoriality

Territoriality is a manifestation of the ego that does not want to be disturbed. Holahan states territoriality is a pattern of behavior related to the ownership or rights of a person or group of people over a certain place or geographical location. This pattern of behavior includes personalization and defense against external interference. (Holahan, 1982), there are three groups, namely:

1. Primary territories are places that are very private and can only be entered by a familiar person.
2. Secondary territories, namely places that are jointly owned by a number of people already know each other.
3. Public territory, namely a place open to the public where everyone is allowed to be in that place.

D. Crowding and Density

Holahan states that density is a spatial constraint while crowding is a subjective response to a tight space. There are two characteristics of the relationship between density and crowding, namely, crowding is a perception of density in terms of the number of people, and crowding is a subjective perception. There are four types of density (Holahan, 1982) namely:

1. Rural density, namely: density inside the house is high, while outside it is low.
2. Suburban density, namely: density inside and outside the house is high.
3. Slum density, namely: high density inside and outside the house.
4. Density of luxury houses, namely: density inside the house is low, medium outside tall.

E. Mental Mapping

According to Holahan, mental maps are: a process that allows storing in memory, recalling and re-elaborating information about real locations and signs about the geographical environment. There are several elements of mental maps (Holahan, 1982), namely:

1. Conspicuous signs (landmarks).
2. Paths that connect one place to another.
3. Meeting points between routes (nodes) such as intersections and T-junctions.
4. Regional boundaries (edges) that differentiate one region from another.
5. The district is a homogeneous area that is different from other areas.

Several factors differentiate mental maps: lifestyle, familiarity with environmental conditions, social familiarity, social class, and gender.

F. Stress

After an individual perceives environmental stimuli, two possibilities occur. The first possibility is that the stimulus is perceived within the individual's tolerance threshold, which causes the individual to be in a homeostatic state. The second possibility is that stimuli are perceived as being beyond the tolerance threshold, which causes stress in the individual.

Thus, perception of the environment greatly influences human behavior. Regarding space, this means that the tendency to perceive space is very necessary for humans regarding virtual boundaries that must be owned or spaces that

cannot be disturbed by others with areas that must be owned. However, space is also considered in terms of constraints by paying attention to space freedom and comfort so that behavior does not experience stress.

IV. CONCLUSION

Perception is the basic process involving human interaction with the environment, and it provides information about the environment (Lang, 1987).

Perceptions are formed due to the interaction of a person (individual) with their life space which ultimately manifests in behavior and attitudes. Thus, the behavior behind human attitudes, responses, and actions is largely determined by the personal perception of the person concerned.

It can be said that human behavior is determined by the psychological conditions within humans in the form of attitudes, perceptions, cognition, and motivation. Cognition is obtained from an individual's culture, experience, and education. The cognitive aspect is the driving aspect of change because the information received determines feelings and willingness to act. In terms of cognition, it consists of several components, namely the cognition component, which will answer the question of what is thought or perceived about objects. The affective conation component will answer what is felt (happy/displeased) towards the object, and the conation component will answer the question of how willingness to act on an object.

Each of these components does not stand alone but forms a unit called a cognitive system. The cognitive system is the result of a cognitive process consisting of the activities of perception, imagination, thinking, reasoning and decision making.

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